

COMET Participant Information

Over 50 volunteer participants across the research metadata community came together to discuss a potential community curation model for research metadata. These individuals represented a variety of stakeholder groups including infrastructure, advocacy organizations, institutions, funders, researchers, government, publishers, and independent consultants. Participants reside in North America, Europe, South America, and Australasia. They identified their expertise as follows:

COMET Participant Expertise

Participants also held a variety of interests related to COMET. They identified these as follows:

COMET Participant Interests

An additional 34 people were informed about the project and/or provided their advice at different stages without committing to be full participants.

The following individuals were initiators and conveners of the Collaborative Metadata Enrichment Taskforce (COMET):

- **Juan Pablo Alperin**, Simon Fraser University
- **Adam Buttrick**, California Digital Library
- **John Chodacki**, California Digital Library
- **Maria Praetzellis**, California Digital Library

Clare Dean was contracted as the Community Outreach Manager.

The following individuals were active participants in COMET and contributed their thoughts and questions during listening sessions and/or through comments on documentation.

- **Isabel Abedrapo Rosen**, Universidad Central de Chile

- **Elizabeth Agee**, US DOE Office of Scientific and Technical Information (OSTI)
- **John Aspler**, Canadian Research Knowledge Network (CRKN)
- **Fred Atherden**, eLife
- **Matt Buys**, DataCite
- **Amélie Church**, Sorbonne University
- **Yvonne Campfens**, OA Switchboard
- **Kyle Demes**, OurResearch
- **Britta Dreyer**, DataCite
- **Nikoline Dohm Lauridsen**, Research Portal Denmark - NORA (National Open Research Analytics)
- **Nancy Fallgren**, National Library of Medicine
- **Rupert Gatti**, Thoth Open Metadata
- **Maria Gould**, DataCite / ROR
- **Ted Habermann**, Metadata Game Changers
- **Melissa Harrison**, EMBL-EBI
- **Ricardo Hartley Belmar**
- **Hannah Hillen**, Thoth Open Metadata
- **Kristi Holmes**, Northwestern University
- **Jackson Huang**, Educopia
- **Cristina Huidiu**, Wageningen University & Research Library
- **Katerina Janderova**, Czech Academy of Sciences, Library
- **Eric Jeangirard**, French Ministry of Higher Education and Research
- **Jamaica Jones**, University of Pittsburgh; CKAN
- **Anne L'Hôte**, French Ministry of Higher Education and Research
- **Tilo Mathes**, Research Space / RSpace
- **Remedios Melero**, Spanish National Research Council
- **Carole Melzac**, ABES France
- **Daniel Nüst**, Technische Universität Dresden | NFDI4Earth, KOMET
- **Priyanka Ojha**, Amsterdam UMC
- **Colin Orian**, Dalhousie University
- **Bhavesh Patel**, FAIR Data Innovations Hub, California Medical Innovations Institute
- **Silvio Peroni**, OpenCitations / University of Bologna
- **Nici Pfeiffer**, Center for Open Science
- **Mark Phillips**, University of North Texas Libraries
- **Vaida Plankytė**, RSpace
- **Iratxe Puebla**, Make Data Count

- **Sheila Rabun**, Lyrasis
- **Eric Olson**, Center for Open Science
- **Howard Ratner**, CHORUS
- **Poppy Riddle**, Dalhousie University
- **Carly Robinson**, United States Department of Energy
- **Cody Ross**, DataCite
- **Mogens Sandfær**, Research Portal Denmark / National Open Research Analytics
- **Eric Schares**, Iowa State University
- **Lisa Schiff**, California Digital Library, University of California Office of the President
- **Arjan Schalken**, UKB / Dutch consortium
- **Paul Shannon**, eLife, Society and The Kotahi Foundation
- **Arthur Smith**, American Physical Society
- **Stephan Stahlschmidt**, German Centre of Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW)
- **Toby Steiner**, Thoth Open Metadata
- **Nees Jan van Eck**, Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University
- **Dave Vieglais**, University of Kansas
- **Tim Vines**, DataSeer
- **Tina von Raesfeld**, Public Library of Science (PLOS)
- **Joe Wass**, Pardalotus Technology
- **Simon Willemin**, ETH Zurich